

REVIEW ON OVARIAN CYSTS IN DAIRY CATTLE, ITS TREATMENT AND PREVENTION

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ABSTRACT

The aim of this review paper was to assess the treatment and prevention methods for ovarian cysts in dairy cattle. The first two months after calving are when dairy cows with ovarian cysts are most frequently seen. The development of large, persistent ovulatory follicles in the ovaries and the inability of a mature follicle to ovulate at the proper time throughout the estrous cycle are traits of these conditions. Although the precise cause of ovarian cysts is unknown, they are frequently linked to heredity, high milk production, age, the duration of lactation, body condition score, seasonality, and phytoestrogens. Using a combination of the patient's medical history, clinical symptoms, transrectal palpation, ultrasound, and plasma or milk progesterone assays, ovarian cysts in dairy cows are detected. . Ovarian cysts in dairy cattle resulted in economic losses due to an increase in the number of days open, an increase in the rate of infertility-related culling, high treatment expenses, and a longer calving interval. Ovarian cysts in dairy cows are a dangerous ailment that regularly impacts the reproductive ability of dairy cows, to sum up. Therefore, the main therapies for cystic ovarian disease in dairy cows are Gonadotrophin-releasing hormone (GnRH), human chorionic Gonadotrophin (HCG), and prostaglandin F2. Cystic ovarian illness can be avoided with careful genetic selection, the removal of bulls whose sire daughters have experienced the condition, and a healthy diet. In order to increase the fertility of dairy cows, it is important to remove bulls whose sire daughters suffer from cystic ovarian disease. Additionally, dairy farmers are required to take the cow to a vet clinic if the cow exhibits typical estrus activity and fails to become pregnant twice or more following insemination

Keywords: Ovarian Cysts, Dairy Cow, Prevention and Treatment

INTRODUCTION

Cattle reproductive failure is known to have several common causes, one of which being ovarian cysts (OC). In the dairy industry, it is incurable because it causes significant financial losses by lengthening the day's open time, increasing treatment expenses, and sometimes culling cows from the herd. Also increases the culling rate and the interval from conception to calving (Grohn *et al.*, 1997). It is characterized by large, persistent ovulatory follicles in the ovaries (Wiltbank *et al.*, 2002). A developing follicle failing to ovulate at the appropriate time throughout the estrous cycle is another characteristic that characterizes it (Ortega *et al.*, 2015). Between 5% and 25% of dairy farms have an incidence of cystic ovarian disease, which is most likely due to different management techniques (Peter, 2004)

The most important characteristics associated with sickness prevalence include heredity, high milk production, age, lactation period, body condition score, seasonality, and phytoestrogens. Additionally, stress, metritis, a retained placenta, milk fever, and metritis all contribute to cystic ovarian disease (Cattaneo *et al.*, 2014). Cows with abnormal postpartum conditions, such as retained fetal membranes, metritis, ketosis and lameness, have a 1.4 to 2.9-fold increased risk of developing cystic ovarian disease. Some of the risk variables include nutrition, uterine infection, aberrant puerperium, high milk output, seasonal fluctuation, and cow parity (Brito and Palmer, 2004)

To identify follicular cysts from luteal cysts, palpation is insufficient. Without using ultrasonography, it is impossible to distinguish between follicular and luteinized cysts in anestrus cows. The accuracy of diagnosing ovarian cysts and distinguishing between follicular and luteal cysts can be increased by combining transrectal palpation of the genital tract to determine that a corpus luteum is absent and the uterus lacks tone with ultrasonography to confirm a corpus luteum is absent, to measure the size of follicles that are present, and to look for luteinization (Bartolome *et al.*, 2005)

Palpation of the reproductive canal is the most typical technique for detecting pregnancy, as opposed to a progesterone assay or ultrasound. It's important to distinguish between cyclic cows that haven't been found in estrus and non-cyclic (true anestrus) cows. The latter is

necessary for the appropriate administration of medicine intended to synchronize oestrus and insemination at a particular time (Eddy, 1977 and Thatcher *et al.*, 1997). The ability to identify pregnancies early is essential for managing reproduction and allowing animals that are not pregnant to breed as soon as is practical. For effective treatment of cystic ovarian degeneration, accurate diagnosis is essential (Dobson & Nanda, 1992)

The most effective treatment for cattle with ovarian cysts at the moment is gonadotropin-releasing hormone (GnRH), which causes the pituitary to generate luteinizing hormone (LH) and luteinize the cyst. Prostaglandin therapy administered later causes luteinized cysts to regress. To that purpose, it is crucial to conduct research on ovarian cysts in dairy cows and study available treatments and preventative measures (Pushp *et al.*, 2016)

CHARACTERISTICS AND ECONOMIC LOSSES OF OVARIAN CYSTS

Ovarian cysts are defined as a growth that is more than 2.5 cm in diameter and has been present on an ovary for more than 10 days. Cysts are simple, fluid-filled sacs with a membrane around them that resemble grapes (Figure 1). The most common time for cows to acquire cystic ovarian disease is the first two months after calving. Although the specific cause is still unknown, ovarian cysts are thought to be induced by a variety of factors, including perpartum stress, age, nutritional deficiencies, and genetic predisposition (Day, 1991). Cows with cystic follicles had high plasma concentrations of progesterone, luteinizing hormone, and estradiol-17 even when ovulation is expected (Hatler *et al.*, 2003)

On practically every dairy farm in the world, the quantity of fatty acids, particularly palmitic and stearic acid, in the serum of ovarian cysts decreases reproductive efficiency. The majority of dairy farms suffer significant financial losses as a result of ovarian cysts decreasing milk output and reproductive efficiency. The research indicates that there are multiple causes of cystic ovarian disease, making it difficult to understand the disease's causes and create an effective treatment (Ortega *et al.*, 2015). Additionally, one of the most prevalent reproductive illnesses in dairy cows and a recognized cause of transient infertility, cystic ovarian disease, have a reported incidence of 6 to 23% (Butler, 2003)

Figure 1: Ovarian Cyst

Calving and first service are postponed by 6 to 11 days and 20 to 30 days, respectively, in cases of cystic ovarian illness compared to normal. It has also been linked to an increased chance of culling. The effects on feed costs, calves' typical growth rates, labor costs, and medical expenses account for the majority of the economic damage caused by the prevalence of ovarian cysts (Gundling *et al.*, 2009). COFs (Cystic Ovarian Follicles) are a prevalent cause of infertility in dairy cows because they prolong the interval between calving. The increased calving period combined with the price of COF treatment results in a loss for the dairy farmer. COF is usually referred to as Cystic Ovarian Disease (Fourichon *et al.*, 2003)

Types of Ovarian cysts in dairy cows

Ovarian cysts are ovulatory ovarian structures having a chamber greater than 20mm in diameter but without a corpus luteum (follicular or luteal). Follicular and luteal cysts (FC and LC) differ in wall thickness by less than 3 mm and more than 3 mm, respectively. The three types of ovarian cysts are follicular cysts, luteal cysts, and cystic corpora lutea (Brito *et al.*, 204)

a. Follicular Cysts

Ovarian follicular cysts are often defined as 2.5 cm or larger follicular forms that last for an undetermined amount of time without a corpus luteum (Youngquist and Threlfall, 2007). Ovarian follicular cysts are defined as follicles with a minimum diameter of 20 mm that are

present in one or both ovaries without a corpus luteum and interrupt cycle. According to Vanholder *et al*, (2006) the characteristics of modern intensive systems, such as increased milk output, metabolic condition of high-producing cows, and management strategies, have changed the clinical aspects of Ovarian follicular cysts and related issues (Vanholder *et al.*, 2006; Braw-Tal *et al.*, 2006)

Figure 1: Ovary containing Follicular cyst characterized by large, thin wall contain serous clear follicular fluid (A) single small cyst (B) large cyst 40 mm in diameter (C) double cyst.

b. Luteinized Cysts

Larger ovaries and one or more cysts with thicker walls than follicular cysts are characteristics of luteal cystic ovarian disease (Kahn, 2010). Ball and Peters (2004) defined luteinized cystic follicles as cysts with thicker walls that secrete substantial amounts of progesterone. They are smooth and rounded, with a spherical chamber surrounded by luteinized cells and encased by fibrous tissue (Schlafer, 2007).

The luteal cyst forms when the follicular cyst's granulosa and theca cells luteinize and start producing progesterone. Age-related increases in luteal cyst incidence are particularly common in cows that produce large amounts of milk (Peter *et al.*, 2009)

Figure 2: Ovary containing large luteal cyst characterized by thick walled contain serous clear follicular fluid (A) double cyst (B) large cyst 50 mm in diameter (C) 22 ml follicular fluid after aspiration from luteinized cyst.

c. Cystic Corpora Luteal

A cow's cystic corpus luteum has a diameter larger than 7 mm (Figure 4). Despite the fact that the former is a normally functional structure and the latter is a pathological condition, the terms for luteal cysts and cystic corpus are frequently confused. Cystic corpus is luteal tissue that originates from a corpus hemorrhagicum and contains fluid in a central cavity luteum (CL). Cystic luteal develops on its own when follicles become luteinized without ovulation (Hamilton *et al.*, 1996).

The phrase corpus luteum with a cavity has thus been suggested in place of the phrase cystic corpus luteum (Chuang *et al.*, 2010). The proportion of cystic corpora lutea (CLs) decreases over the course of the estrous cycle and ranges from 25.2% to 78.8% during diestrus. Because they are found in cows that are typically cyclic or pregnant, cystic corpora lutea are regarded as a typical stage or variant of CL development. In contrast to the homogeneous, liver-like firmness of a typical CL's base, cystic CL have a soft, mushy core area because of the presence of fluid from a degenerating blood clot. Cystic CLs aren't pathogenic, thus a diagnosis isn't necessary and they don't need to be treated, but 5-7 days after estrus is the optimum period to notice the structure.

Cause of Ovarian Cysts

Ovarian cysts are one of the most frequent causes of infertility in dairy cows, and they are associated with a large economic loss due to their high incidence, longer days to first service, and longer days open (Lopez-Diaz, 1996). Between 5 and 25%, dairy farms have an incidence of ovarian disease that ranges from 2.7% to 15.1%, most likely due to different management techniques (Cattaneo *et al.*, 2014)

Additionally, it is considered high since different herds have differing estimates of the disease's prevalence, which ranges from 10% to 30% (Vanholder *et al.*, 2006; Grado-Ahuir *et al.*, 2011). Lower milk production cows were more likely to recover on their own during the puerperal stage. Milk production was noticeably increased in growing cows. Although it appears that endogenous and/or exogenous stimuli can change the hypothalamo-pituitary-gonadal axis, resulting in cyst formation, the exact cause of ovarian cysts is unknown at this time (Amweg *et al.*, 2013)

The most important characteristics associated with sickness prevalence include heredity, high milk production, age, lactation period, body condition score, seasonality, and phytoestrogens. However, it has been noted that stress, metritis, milk fever, and retained placenta all play a part (Cattaneo *et al.*, 2014). Additionally, a combination of genetic traits, milk production, stress, and an unbalanced diet might result in cystic ovaries (Crane *et al.*, 2006 and Jeengar *et al.*, 2014).

Cows are predisposed to developing follicular cysts due to genetics, hormonal imbalances, and external causes, but the most widely accepted theory is that Cystic ovarian disease is brought on

by a neuroendocrine imbalance involving the hypothalamic hypophyseal gonadil-axis (Hooijer *et al.*, 2001)

Diagnosis of Ovarian Cysts

Ovarian cysts in cows can be identified using the history and clinical symptoms, transrectal palpation, ultrasonography, and plasma or milk progesterone testing (Peter, 2004). Cysts found in the ovaries before the puerperium had no effect on reproduction, but those found during the puerperium had a detrimental effect on fertility (Gossen and Hoed, 2006). The most likely time for a diagnosis in high-yielding dairy cows is 30 to 60 days after parturition; however the existence of ovulatory follicles in the first few weeks following calving should not be confused with ovarian insufficiency. In actuality, if ovulatory follicles are discovered no sooner than seven weeks after calving, when reproductive capacity is meant to be restored, an ovarian impairment may be taken into consideration (Sheldon and Dobson, 2004)

The accuracy of the diagnosis can be increased by obtaining data on the animal's reproductive history, vaginal examination, and progesterone testing. Follicular and luteal cysts can be found with ultrasound with good sensitivity (Hanzen *et al.*, 2000). Because follicular and luteal cysts are similar in size and function, it may be challenging to distinguish between them. A proper diagnosis is made by physical examination, ultrasound, and plasma progesterone tests: determining that the uterus lacks tone and the corpus luteum is missing using per rectum palpitation of the genital tract; Measurement of plasma progesterone concentration to assess the level of luteinization and ultrasonography to confirm the absence of a corpus luteum and assess the size of any existing follicles (Bartolome *et al.*, 2005)

On the basis of the quantity and size of the follicles, the presence of follicular waves, the body condition score and the stage of lactation, ovarian cysts are distinguished from shallow anestrus (Bartolome *et al.*, 2005). Ovarian cysts are straightforward to diagnose, although it can be challenging to accurately distinguish between follicular and luteal forms (Hanzen *et al.*, 2000).

The suspected animal's reproductive history and previous reproductive problem treatments, along with an ultrasound exam, can then be utilized as a foundation for a diagnosis (Peters *et al.*, 2009)

Progesterone levels in the peripheral circulation are typically related with relatively high concentrations of luteal cysts and relatively low amounts of follicular cysts. The minimal plasma Progesterone 4(P4) concentration for a cyst to be deemed luteal, according to many researchers, is greater than 1ng/ml. Therefore, a combination of diagnostic techniques, including transrectal palpation, transrectal ultrasound, and plasma progesterone profiles, is necessary for an accurate identification of the type of Ovarian cysts (Santos *et al.*, 2000)

TREATMENT OF CYSTIC OVARIAN DISEASE

a. Gonadotrophin releasing Hormone (GnRH)

The best treatment is gonadotrophin-releasing hormone (GnRH), which causes luteal hormone (LH) to be released (Roche *et al.*, 1997). According to Eissa and El-Belely (1995), a single GnRH therapy was not as successful as repeated treatments spaced seven days apart. In general, three weeks following GnRH administration, 60% to 95% of treated cows resume their regular oestrus cycle, and then 60% to 85% of them become pregnant (Mollo *et al.*, 2012) The best course of treatment for ovarian cysts in dairy cattle is administration of GnRH coupled with potassium iodide diet (Pushp *et al.*, 2016)

b. Human Chorionic Gonadotrophin (HCG)

Because of the high luteinizing hormone (LH) activity of human chorionic gonadotrophin (HCG), it is employed (Kasler and Graverick, 1982). GnRH medication has not been effective in treating refractory cysts, hence the HCG molecule has been employed instead (Peter, 2004). Because most cystic cows heal within two weeks and get pregnant within three inseminations, long-acting gestagen treatment has a high success rate (Mollo *et al.*, 2012). According to a report, cystic dairy cows respond equally to the therapeutic effects of HCG and GnRH (De Rensis *et al.*, 2010)

c. Prostaglandin F2 α (PGF2 α)

PGF2 is employed because of its luteolytic activity, which shrinks the corpus luteum and allows the development of dominant follicles on the ovary, which results in estrus and ovulation 72 to

96 hours after administration. PGF₂ is widely used to treat conditions like endometritis, pyometra, luteal cystic ovarian disease, mummification, and persistent corpus luteum. In an effort to boost reproductive efficiency, it has become common practice to administer PGF₂ or a chemical comparable to it to cows shortly after giving birth (Parmar *et al.*, 2016)

Only luteinized cysts should be treated with prostaglandin F_{2a} (PGF₂ a), as it causes luteinized cysts to retreat, resulting in oestrus 2 or 3 days following therapy (Kasler and Graverick, 1982). Treatment of choice for luteal cysts is the use of prostaglandin F₂ (PGF₂) or its equivalents (Hanzen *et al.*, 2000). Additionally, this medication could be used in conjunction with GnRH/hCG to treat follicular cysts and shorten the induced luteal phase (Jeengar *et al.*, 2014)

The best treatment for luteal cysts is luteolytic dosages of PGF₂, with estrus being visible in 3-5 days (Kahn, 2010). Progesterone therapy was thought to have effects via restoring the hypothalamo-pituitary axis' capacity to produce an LH surge in response to rising estradiol levels (Todoroki and Kaneko, 2006). Moreover, the percentage of cows developing OC dropped from 25% to 3% when progesterone was utilized for estrus synchronization following embryo collection instead of PGF₂ (Brito and Palme, 2004)

Prevention of Cystic Ovarian Disease in dairy cows

One way to prevent cystic ovarian disease is through careful genetic selection and the eradication of bulls whose daughters have the disease. Ideally, cystic ovaries should not be treated in cows, and their offspring should not be used for breeding (Kesler and Garverick, 1982)

In addition to a healthy diet, preventive must start with a condition assessment halfway during the preceding lactation. During the second half of lactation, at dry off, cows should be fed to a score of 3.5 to 3.75 and kept there until calving. A healthy body reserve will lessen the unfavorable energy balance that occurs during early lactation. Close-up meals must be created with the intention of reducing the development of post-calving problems including abomasum displacement, ketosis, and hypocalcaemia. Numerous studies have shown the advantages of supplementary selenium in maintaining immunological competence against cystic ovarian disease, coupled with vitamin A, vitamin E, and beta-carotene (Geoffrey, 2001)

CONCLUSION:

This review article was assessed the strategies for ovarian cyst treatment and prevention in dairy cattle. Due to the significant financial losses it causes the dairy industry, ovarian cysts are a serious and prevalent problem in dairy cows. This condition is of major concern to the dairy industry as a whole. It reduces milk production and costs the dairy sector money by extending the number of days open, increasing the rate at which animals are killed due to infertility, and rising treatment costs.

RECOMMENDATIONS:

- ✓ Dairy cow fertility can be increased by removing bulls whose sire daughters have cystic ovarian illness.
- ✓ Dairy farmers should be made aware of the problem and should take the cow to a vet clinic if a cow exhibits typical estrus activity and is unable to conceive twice or more following insemination

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